

PERSONAL INSURANCE STATUS AND ISSUES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction

Due to the development of the insurance system in our country, the legal basis and guarantees created for the entities engaged in this activity, their place and role in our economy is increasing more and more. The current trends of economic development, the specific characteristics of insurance companies' activities require the search for ways to increase insurance reserves and increase the efficiency of insurance companies' activities.

Many international insurance organizations have been established worldwide, and their activities are aimed at developing the insurance market and improving the quality of insurance relations.

In the development of the world, the insurance system is an important strategic network that ensures the well-being of the state and socially protects the population and its property. One of the urgent tasks of today is to develop the insurance system in a sustainable and stable manner, as well as the banking, financial and tax systems that exist in the economic sector of any country. In order to develop the insurance system and improve the activities of insurance companies in our country, independent insurance companies were established in the insurance market. Before the years of independence, there was a single state insurance organization in our country, and insurance was not voluntary, but compulsory. Today, state, joint and private insurance companies have been established in our republic in order to create a competitive environment in every field. The services provided in the insurance market provide economic assistance in protecting enterprises of various types of ownership from unexpected natural phenomena, and in timely and full compensation of the consequences of the damage. Businesses of different types of ownership are trying to use insurance services on a large scale in order to prevent various unexpected and accidental losses and for their stable

operation in order to effectively use their existing assets. Therefore, the demand for insurance services is increasing nowadays.

Material and Methods

In the years of Uzbekistan's independence, special importance has been attached to the development of insurance, especially personal insurance. In this regard, the necessary legal-normative basis of insurance relations, relevant state programs, road maps have been developed and are being implemented. In particular, Resolution PQ-4412 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2019 is aimed at further reforming the national insurance market and ensuring its rapid development, introducing new types of insurance services with high demand, and ensuring the increase of consumer confidence in the insurance market. and the main directions of rapid development:

- improvement of the legal framework in the insurance sector;
- increase the level of capitalization, solvency and financial stability of the professional participants of the insurance market;
- development and expansion of insurance market infrastructure;
- to strengthen the protection of the rights of consumers of insurance services and other subjects of insurance activity;
- to increase the volume, types, expansion and quality of the provided insurance services through the introduction of new innovative insurance products and the development of traditional products in high demand;
- active introduction and development of electronic types of insurance services using modern information technologies;
- improvement of the system of training and retraining of insurance market specialists and improving their qualifications, stimulating research activities;
- it was decided to create a positive image of the national insurance market and increase its investment attractiveness through integration with international insurance markets.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that there are several tasks aimed at the development of the personal insurance sector, which are waiting for their solution, including:

- a) in the direction of improving the regulatory framework:
 - improvement of voluntary pension insurance mechanisms, increasing the level of pension provision of citizens by introducing voluntary pension types and mechanisms;
 - establishment of a life insurance payment guarantee fund;
 - the insurer may expand the list of investment instruments and etc.

b) in the direction of expanding the size and scope of insurance services and improving the quality of insurance:

- development of new innovative types of insurance services, in particular: insurance against oncological and acute diseases with the possibility of organizing the treatment of the insured person abroad in the life insurance network, insurance for saving the life of a child for higher education through the system of indexation and hedging of funds, in case of child birth and insured long-term life insurance, investment life insurance (unit linked), which provides for the payment of the insurance amount when the person reaches the age of adulthood.

In addition, the expansion of insurance product sales channels, including the use of the “Cashback” system mobile application, the training of specialized insurance specialists and other tasks are aimed at improving the quality of insurance, especially personal insurance, and increasing its attractiveness.

On November 23, 2021, the newly amended Law “On Insurance Activities” adopted by the Legislative Chamber and approved by the Senate. In order to improve the quality of the life insurance sector and personal insurance, the law includes, among other things, the attachment of electronic policies by law, the introduction of international rating practices to insurance companies, clarification of the terms used in insurance contractual relations, clarification of the legal basis of contractual relations for medical insurance, life insurance and other types of personal insurance and creates a basis for further increasing the quality of insurance, strengthening the integration of the insurance industry into the international market.

Results

As for the state of the insurance market, according to the dynamics of insurance income, the growth rate of insurance income in 2017-2021 is in a stable state, and by the end of 2018, insurance income made the highest increase compared to the previous year, i.e. 176%. By the end of 2021, the income indicator increased by 168% compared to 2020 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of total income of the insurance market of Uzbekistan in years, billion soums

The share of personal insurance in the total insurance income is not high (Figure 2), although the share of personal insurance income in the total income in the world market is more than 70%.

Figure 2. The share of personal insurance in the total insurance income of Uzbekistan, %

Figure 3. Life insurance product revenue per capita in 2021, in USD

Analyzing insurance income per capita, insurance income per person in Uzbekistan in 2018-2021 averaged 6-10 US dollars. If we analyze the insurance income for life insurance products, the insurance income per capita in Uzbekistan is very low, that is, equal to 2 US dollars. (Figure 3).

Table 1 shows the state of the insurance market in terms of insurance income over the last three years. It is also possible to analyze the change in the level of insurance penetration. The share of personal insurance income in GDP remained low at around 0.1% during these periods.

Table-1.

Insurance penetration level and income indicators for insurance products in Uzbekistan

Insurance types	Insurance premiums, million soms			Share in GDP, %		
	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021
By type of total insurance, including:	2 313 903	2 213 713,2	3 732 845	0,45%	0,38%	0,51%
Total by types of personal insurance	620 339	367 522,6	776 363	0,1%	0,06%	0,1%

The personal insurance coverage of the population was 5% in 2019, and 4.2% in 2020. It was determined that 4.5% of the population will use personal insurance services in 2021. Comparing this analysis to WHO data, within the countries studied, around 15% of the population spends on medical expenses out of their own pocket, which means that the remaining 75% of the population is covered by personal insurance. In Uzbekistan, personal insurance coverage in general is around 4-5% on average over the last three years. This is very low compared to world standards. From this, it can be concluded that, despite the fact that enough decisions have been made to increase the scope of this sector, the functions of the sector participants and state control within their authority are not sufficiently implemented. In our opinion, this situation calls for a fundamental revision of powers.

Discussion

By the end of 2021, the GDP of Uzbekistan amounted to 734.6 trillion soms. Analyzing the penetration and density of personal insurance, the share of insurance in GDP by the end of 2021 was equal to 0.5%. This means the penetration of insurance, and this indicator was 7% in the world during this period. The share of personal insurance in GDP was 0.1% in Uzbekistan and 5% in the world. When analyzing insurance income, by the end of 2021, personal insurance income per capita was \$2 in Uzbekistan and \$628 in the world. Table 2.2 presents a comparative analysis of important macroeconomic indicators of the private insurance market in Uzbekistan and the world as of the beginning of 2022. Based on this analysis, it is possible to plan future growth indicators of the personal insurance industry of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

Based on the above analysis, we conclude that the personal insurance sector of Uzbekistan has great potential. It should be noted that several tasks are waiting to

be solved in the state measures aimed at the development of the private insurance sector in expanding the scope of this sector.

Some issues envisaged in the economic reforms are awaiting their solution, including improvement of the legal framework in the insurance sector, development and expansion of the insurance market infrastructure, introduction of new innovative insurance products, active introduction of electronic types of insurance services, training and retraining of insurance market specialists and improving the system of their professional development, stimulating scientific research activities, forming a positive image of the national insurance market, reforming the field of insurance methodology, etc.

In particular, the establishment of a life insurance payment guarantee fund, the development of new innovative types of insurance services, the training of narrow specialists in insurance work, the expansion of sales channels, the active introduction and development of electronic types of insurance services using modern information technologies, and the formation of a positive image of the national insurance market. remains an important task facing management.

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